

Photographs or Mobile Maps?

Displaying Landmarks in Pedestrian Navigation Systems

Christina Ohm, Bernd Ludwig, Saskia Gerstmeier

Chair of Information Science, Universität Regensburg
Universitätsstraße 31, 93053 Regensburg, Germany
{christina.ohm, bernd.ludwig}@ur.de, saskia.gerstmeier@stud.uni-r.de

Abstract

Research Question: Should photographs of landmarks be displayed in indoor pedestrian navigation systems? At which point of the navigational task can these interfaces support the user?

Approach: Two different navigation prototypes were implemented: one of them used photographs of landmarks to explain the route, whereas the other one showed a mobile map.

Method: The time it took the users to orient themselves was recorded with the smartphone application and served as a depended variable.

Results: Users performed significantly better with the navigation prototype using photographs, especially if the navigation instruction is given at a route point with a high branching factor and thus high complexity.

Keywords: Landmarks, Pedestrian navigation systems, Wayfinding

1 Motivation

It is a proven fact that pedestrians prefer route instructions based on salient objects, usually referred to as landmarks in wayfinding and pedestrian navigation literature (Raubal & Winter 2002, Winter 2003, Winter et al. 2004,

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Miller & Carlson 2011). Therefore, pedestrian navigation systems should use landmarks to guide the user along a route. Alongside with the problem of calculating routes, which is a research topic on its own right, the question arises how landmarks should be displayed in order to support the user in an optimal way during the navigational task. It is state of the art to display the environment and calculated routes in navigation systems with maps. These can also be enriched with an abstract graphical representation of landmarks (Elias & Paelke 2008). In contrast to this very schematic display, Wenig & Malaka 2010 claim that photographs can be used to assist the user during navigation. Beeharee & Steed (2006) and Hile et al. (2008) showed that especially at so-called decision points, i.e. points along the route where the user has to decide whether to change direction or not, pictures can help to find one's way. Since this research was done in outdoor environments, the results are not easily applicable to indoor areas. For instance, instruction of pedestrian navigation systems in indoor environments require a higher density of landmarks, as the routes usually contain more turns of direction (Radoczky 2007). Moreover, in these areas landmarks can be chosen from a small set of categories despite the high diversity of distinct objects (Brunner-Friedrich & Radoczky 2006). Photographs could help the user to unambiguously identify landmarks in this difficult situation. Therefore, the study presented in this paper examines whether photographs of landmarks are helpful in indoor environments to assist the user compared to mobile map representations. The paper is organized as follows: first of all, current pedestrian navigation systems in outdoor and indoor areas are presented and discussed with respect to our research approach. Afterwards, the conducted study is described and results are presented. Finally, the findings are discussed concerning their implications for pedestrian navigation systems.

2 Related work

Several navigation prototypes exist for indoor and outdoor environments, whereas exploring different interfaces and having in mind various research questions. In the following two sections concerning indoor and outdoor pedestrian navigation systems, several lines of research are described and their implications for the study presented in this paper are outlined.

2.1 Outdoor pedestrian navigation systems

With regard to outdoor areas, numerous studies compare mobile map representations to other non-standard interface types. For instance, Partala & Salminen (2012) evaluate three different user interfaces, including one “traditional” graphical map, a photorealistic satellite map and a photorealistic street level view. They come to the conclusion that photorealistic interfaces provide a better user experience than traditional maps, but cause more workload during navigation. Furthermore, the pragmatic quality, i.e. the usability, is rated significantly lower compared to the mobile map interface. However, the street level view, and thus the most realistic and picture-like depiction, helps to identify landmarks best.

In the study of Walther-Franks & Malaka (2008) a mobile map view is compared to an augmented reality interface. Pictures of the current scene enhanced with arrows that indicate the direction were received as more useful than the mobile map representation. An analogous study was conducted a few years later by Rehr et al. (2012). In contrast to Walther-Franks & Malaka (2008), the augmented reality interface did not include directional arrows, but gave visual hints at landmarks by using circular markers. Participants performed significantly worse with the augmented reality interface in terms of workload and completion time. Mulloni et al. 2011 showed that augmented reality interfaces with direction arrows are mostly used by the participants at intersections.

Already in 2006 Beeharee und Steed compared a system that used photos of landmarks to a mobile map representation and found out that these pictures can help to support wayfinding. Similar results were drawn by Hile et al. (2008), however, both studies were rather explorative.

Taking into account the findings of the presented outdoor studies, it is not clear whether, and in particular when, photorealistic graphical representations should be used by pedestrian navigation systems. To some extent the results are inconsistent with one another, which is of course influenced by different designs, study aims and interfaces. Nevertheless, the findings give strong hints that pictures of landmarks can be of help for pedestrians during the navigation task. However, are these results applicable for indoor environments, which tend to differ from outdoor areas as stated in the introduction? With this in mind, the next section shows an overview of studies conducted in indoor environments.

2.2 Indoor pedestrian navigation systems

Considering studies conducted in indoor environments, a lot of research examines the suitability of different mobile map representations. In particular, Bouwer et al. 2012 implemented a prototype for a fair. Even though they found out that participants effectively reach their destination with their UI, they argue that people have problems to initially orient themselves at the beginning of the navigational task and that salient objects (i.e. the stands of the fair) cannot be identified by the test persons. Especially the latter is consistent with the findings of Puikkonen et al. (2009). Möller et al. (2013) have implemented an augmented reality application that shows panorama pictures enhanced with directional arrows at decision points inside of a university building. They additionally conducted a user study and achieved relatively high values for user satisfaction and efficiency. In conclusion, these studies focus on usability evaluation of one navigational aid and therefore no insights can be gained about the suitability of each interface type with regard to the current navigation step.

Another line of research in indoor areas once again examines mobile map presentations, but rather to examine these depictions on their own, other visualization techniques are also included. For instance, Taher and Cheverst (2011) compare mobile map representations to three-dimensional depictions of the environment. Their results show that salient objects are more likely to be used as reference points for navigation if participants used the 3D-interface. Thus, landmarks are more easily recognizable in three-dimensional and therefore more photorealistic interfaces. Still, test persons stated that they would prefer to have the option to see the map at any point of the navigational task. Similarly, Münzer & Stahl (2011) concluded that both, mobile map presentation and 3D-interfaces can efficiently assist the user.

All in all, with regard to outdoor studies, there is little research on photo-realistic graphical representations in indoor environments. In particular, research for indoor environments similar to the study of Beeharee und Steed already conducted in 2006 in outdoor environments was not performed yet. Accordingly, we tried to fill this gap with our work presented in this paper. We conducted a user study that evaluated a system that shows photos of a landmark and compared it to an interface that depicts a mobile map. The details of the study and the results are discussed in the next section.

3 Study on the depiction of landmarks

Considering the findings of the related work, we wanted to evaluate if, and at which navigation point, photos of landmarks can be helpful during the navigation and wayfinding task. Therefore, we conducted a study with a between subject design. Each test person was assigned to one of the interfaces described below. The landmarks used in the main study were collected in a pre-study, on which is reported in the next subsection. Subsequently, details concerning the experimental design and the results of the main study are presented.

3.1 Pre-study on landmark selection

The landmarks used in the main study were collected in a pre-study with twelve participants (5 males, 7 females). Their mean age was 25 (min: 21, max: 30). According to the test design to collect landmarks by Sefelin et al. (2005), participants were asked to accomplish the route, where the main experiment should take place, twice (see fig. 1). In the first run participants followed the instructor and were told to look closely at their surroundings and try to remember objects, since they have to describe the route afterwards. Consequently, the test person's attention was directed to objects that can serve as landmarks. Afterwards, participants once again followed the route, but this time they had to name salient objects. This data was recorded manually. All in all, participants named 31 landmarks. After eliminating only temporally available objects like Christmas decoration from the set, the test route was segmented in more or less equally distant route parts taking into account that some instructions like changes of directions or floors necessarily have to be given. Afterwards, for each of the seven resulting sections, the salient object that was named most frequently was selected and therefore used for the main study. More precisely, the landmarks are:

- Trachten Pöllinger (shop)
- Stairs in the second floor
- Elevator in the first floor
- Kräuterhexe (shop)
- Palmers (shop)
- Stairs in the first floor
- Glöckl (shop/ restaurant)

3.2 Main study

According to our primary research interest, the main study was conducted to test the following hypothesis for validity:

H₁: Pedestrians are able to recognize faster where they have to go with interfaces showing photographs of landmarks compared to mobile map representations enriched with landmarks.

The next subsections describe the experimental set-up, the interface prototypes and the achieved results.

Experimental Set-Up

Our study was carried out in a shopping mall, because of the high number of landmarks available in these environments, i.e. mainly shops and functional landmarks like stairs and elevators. Moreover, besides large public buildings like universities or airports, shopping malls are potential application fields for indoor pedestrian navigation systems (Radoczky 2007). The test route included one floor transition and four direction changes (see fig. 1). 43 participants (19 female; 24 male) with a minimum age of 17 years and a maximum of 48 years participated in the study. For the main test they used an Android smartphone provided by the test supervisor. To avoid bias caused by possible previous spatial knowledge, the destination of the route was not told.

Figure 1. Test route (S = start; E = end). Numbers indicate the selected landmarks.

Interface and system prototype

The selected landmarks of the pre-study were first of all included in textual navigation instructions. These instructions were equally structured: they included one landmark and a phrase clarifying the direction. An exemplary instruction is shown in figure 2 labeled with “1”, which says “Go left up the stairs”. In addition to this, the prototypes showed either a mobile map repre-

sentation or a photograph of the landmark (see fig. 2, label “2” and “3”), while the text instructions did not differ. The map representation additionally showed the current route segment with a red line and the landmark with an icon and a checkered flag indicating the end of the current navigation sub-task.

Figure 2. System prototypes used for the main study.

We used photos of landmarks but not of decision points, i.e. photos that not include intersections and different landmarks for the second UI. This is not only motivated by the study of Beeharee & Steed (2006), but also by another consideration: with the computational power of modern smartphones and the broad connections to the web, a scenario, where any user can take and upload a picture of a landmark that can be used in route instructions is feasible. This “Collaborative Landmark Mining” (Bienk et al. 2013) approach is a research purpose on its own right and thus just mentioned here without further specification. No localization system was used so that participants had to click a button when they reached the destination of the instruction to get a new one (see fig. 2, label “4”, marked in German with “Target reached”). In addition to this, another button is shown on the screen which says “Target recognized” (fig. 2, label “5”). This UI element had to be clicked as soon as the test user understood where to go. The time he or she needed to orient him- or herself was used as our main dependent variable. This duration is not influenced by walking speed or other uncontrollable

variables in a real world experiment and therefore represents more precisely which interface helps more to support the navigation task.

Results

To test H_1 for validity, we measured the time it took the users to recognize and understand where they are supposed to go, collected by pushing the button “Target recognized”. Having performed the Shapiro-Wilk test, the statistical assumption of normality had to be rejected for both, the map and the photo interface ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, a Mann-Whitney-U-Test was used. It turned out that participants performed slightly better with the photo interface taking into account the whole navigation task ($p = 0.045$). Thus, the Null-hypothesis can be rejected.

In order to gain detailed findings, the Mann-Whitney-U-Test was conducted for each of the seven steps. As shown in table 1, differences for landmark 1 (shop), 3 (elevator) and 6 (stairs) were detected. In these cases users with the photo interface performed significantly better.

In addition, the branching factors, which can be understood as the number of possible routes the user can take at a specific situation, for each route point was determined. Participants performed better with the photorealistic user interface when the complexity of the decision point is rather high with a branching factor > 3 (see table 1). These findings are perfectly in line with the outdoor studies of, for instance, Mulloni et al. (2011), Partala & Salminen, Beeharee & Steed (2006) or Hile et al. (2008), who showed that photorealistic interfaces helped to identify landmarks and are most likely to be used at intersections, i.e. point with a high complexity.

Table 1. Results separated by landmark, testing differences of the interfaces “map”- “photograph” and mapping to branching factor of the decision point.

Landmark	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
p-value	0.029	0.515	0.044	0.404	0.422	0.027	0.490
Branching Factor	4	3	5	2	2	5	3

4 Conclusion and discussion

In this paper we reported on a study that was conducted in a shopping mall with 43 participants using either a navigational prototype with a mobile map representation enhanced with landmarks or an interface presenting photographs. Our results show that test persons perform significantly better with the photorealistic UI, especially if the route instruction is given at a decision point with a high branching factor and thus a high degree of complexity. This underpins the research done in outdoor environments. The results also imply that pedestrian navigation systems should adapt to the user's navigational context in order to support him or her best possible while wayfinding, which is in any way a cognitively demanding task. Certainly, the study had some limitations: since it was conducted in a shopping mall, the findings cannot be readily applied to other indoor areas like university buildings or hospitals without further investigations. Moreover, the test route consisted of only seven decision points. It would be advantageous to conduct similar studies with more route points in order to gain more generalizable results.

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